

Organizational Culture and Effective Administration of Public Universities in Rivers State

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Abstract

This study examined the relationship between organizational culture and effective administration of public universities in Rivers State, Nigeria. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. A correlational design was adopted. The population of the study comprised academic and non-teaching staff of the three public universities in Rivers State, the total population therefore, embraced 3 vice-chancellors and 5565 academic and non-teaching staff of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rivers State University, and University of Port Harcourt respectively. The sample for this study consists of 373 staff in the three public universities in Rivers State (3 vice-chancellors, 200 academic and 170 non-teaching staff) who were stratified by the location of schools in the public universities in Rivers State. The sample was selected using the Taro Yamane sample size selection method, representing 6.7 percent of the total population. The instrument of the study was a questionnaire structured into two parts. Part one addresses organizational culture tagged organizational culture questionnaire (OCQ) while part two addresses effective administration tagged effective administration of public Universities questionnaire (EAPUQ). The instrument consists of 10 items structured using a 4-point Likert rating scale of strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and strongly disagree (D). Data collected was analyzed using the Statistical Package of the Social Science (SPSS) version 21 of a computer program. While descriptive statistics (Mean and standard deviation) were used to analyze the research questions; the Pearson Product Moment Coefficient was used to analyze the hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance, Cronbach Alpha Coefficient was used to determine the reliability index. Findings revealed that prevalent organizational culture determines the effective administration of public universities in Rivers State, it also revealed that recognition and performance appraisal culture lead to the effective administration of public universities in Rivers State. This showed that a significant relationship exists between organizational culture and effective administration of public universities in Rivers State.

Keywords: Organizational Culture, Shared Beliefs, Behavioural Norms, Effective Administration, Public Universities, Rivers State, Nigeria.

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INTRODUCTION

Organization is a controlled group of people working together with a particular aim of achieving set goals. An organization usually has unique style of functioning which often constitutes its culture. A well organized, structured, managed organization always sees the employees as the most valuable assets whose quality determine the success of the organization and the degree of their commitment to their work in an organization could be influence by the existing values, traditions, beliefs, ideologies, custom, principles which made up of organizational culture either positively or negatively. Culture is the social behaviour and norms found in human society which plays the role of guide that makes human beings conform to an accepted way of life. As culture guides the societies are so it is in every well managed organization. Organizational culture becomes visible through the beliefs, values, attitudes and behavioural pattern of its members. This form the core identity of the organization helps in shaping the behaviour of the employees.

Schein (2004) organizational culture is the underlying beliefs, perceptions, values and ways of interacting that contribute to the unique social and psychological environment of an organization. These unique social phenomena is evidence in organization's customary dresses, mode of communications or languages, behaviour, viewpoint, standards, perceptions, secret code or signs of status and right, myths, ceremonies, and rituals. This means that the people's ways of life can be a strong reason in maximizing the value of human capital which can ultimately be managed for increase in productivity for organizational achievement.

Organizational culture in schools refers to the invasive system of values, beliefs, and norms that exist which can motivate and de-motivate effective performance. Good organizational culture in the schools makes the schools tops among its competitors (Ololube, 2024). This means every university with a well positive organizational culture creates room for staff professional development, achievement, recognition, personal growth as well as work challenges and responsibilities which could in turn lead to effective performance. Ahiauzu (1999) noted that organizational culture generally induced collective mental programming which all the staff of school shared. The school as a system and as organization is expected to have its culture which must be nurtured and sustained for the overall achievement of the educational goals.

In this regard the leadership of the schools needs culture to be able to harness them to bring about high level of job commitment for effective administration and performance from the staff. On the other hand, schools without a positive organizational culture do not value professional development of staff and students. They resist change, and do not values staff development, achievement, recognition, job responsibility as well as personal growth. Organizational culture can be use to increase effectiveness in the administration of organization because it enables the administrators as well as the members to make decisions which will shape the relationship, working progress and decision making and problem solving effectiveness and competitive position in its environment.

The four dimensions of organizational culture as identified by Ololube (2024) include:

- Power dimension which view the organization culture base on unfairness of access to redemption.
- Role dimension is basically on job description and area of discipline
- Achievement dimension refers to task culture which aims at achieving predetermined organization goals.

- The support dimension emphasis on organizational climate that is based on neutral trust between the individual and the organization.

In relation to the school, Hargreaves (1995) stated school as organization has culture as the nucleus controlling the behaviours which assists in the achievement of the school efficiency. He concluded that the effectiveness of the school is determined by the prevalent organizational culture. As a result the school authority and the administrators need to understand that strong culture is beneficial to the overall achievement of the school objectives.

Effectiveness simply refers to the capability of producing a desired result or the ability to produce desired output or objectives are achieved and the level at which targeted problems are solved or simply put effectiveness means doing the right thing (Ololube 2006). Effective administration of university simply means providing or enhancing favorable environment for all academic issues. This academic issue includes teaching, learning, administration, students' motivation and community involvement, sports, leadership position, representative position as well as the effects structure and staff background in the achievement of university goals.

An effective administration basically means the strategic planning and management of school resources to achieve results. This means the success of every universities depends on the effective administration which is left in the custody of the administrator or the vice chancellor and his team and is their responsibility to ensure that as an administrator they should delimited their focus to only academic achievement but also on staff and students background which some time determine their achievement in other academic activities.

Statement of the Problem

Organizational culture no doubt, is an essential ingredient that determines the effective administration of public university; this means the absence of a well laid down culture in public universities in Rivers State to some extent may affect the administration of public universities negatively. It is revealed that, improper consideration to prevalent culture, shared beliefs, behavioural norms, recognitions culture and staff performance appraisal leads to underachievement of the universities predetermined goals and objectives. Cause of this failure or underachievement are often traced to the fact that good number of the universities administrators are bereft of organizational culture to maintain which often leads to inadequate consideration to the professional development of staff and students. For that reason staff and students resist change and work at cross purpose and thus show a lackadaisical attitude towards the achievement of the overall educational goals. The absence of organizational culture in the universities also leads to disunity, low staff morale as well as team spirit, negative behavior among staff and students, poor communication. However, the knowledge of the prevalent core values in the universities can prevent possible internal and external conflict. The question therefore is what steps could be taken to enhance the effective administration of public universities in Rivers State? Did the effective administration of the public universities in Rivers State base on the prevalent organizational culture, shared beliefs, behavioural norms, recognition culture and staff performance appraisal culture? This study therefore, focuses its investigations on two important variables organizational culture and effective administration of public universities in Rivers State.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

This study aims at examined the relationship between the organizational culture and effective administration of public universities in Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought to:

- Ascertain the relationship between organizational shared beliefs and effective administration of public- universities in Rivers State.
- Find out the relationship between organizational behavioural norms and effective administration of public- universities in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study:

- What is the relationship' between the organizational shared beliefs and the effective administration of public universities in Rivers State?
- What is the relationship between the organizational behavioural norms and effective administration of public universities in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses postulated guide the direction of the study at .05 levels of significance:

- There is no significant relationship between organizational shared beliefs and effective administration of public universities in Rivers State.
- There is no significant relationship between behavioural norms and effective administration of public universities in Rivers State.

Significance of the Study

This study shall contribute knowledge to the existing knowledge in education by equipping the school authority, those vested with the administration of the universities to understand that a strong organization culture is important in the effective administration of universities for the overall achievement of the school objective because the quality of the organization culture is a water tied that held the organization together and prevent it from falling apart, gives the organization the potency to deal with thorny challenges and makes the organization unique

It is also key to note that universities with good organization culture live peacefully through shared values and principles that the members abide by in every decision, organizational growth comes through creativity and innovation, stability through motivation of employees, sense of direction through the laid out values, beliefs and goals which the employees work towards while identity comes through brand image.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework that formed the basis of this study is that of Schein theory (1985), Schein described culture as “a prototype of basic assumption, created by a given group of people,’ as it learns to cope with its problem of external- adaption and internal- integration, that has worked- well -enough to be considered’ valid and, therefore is to be taught to new members as a correct way to distinguish, think, and feel’ in relation to these problems”. To Schein, (1988), the essence of culture is its core of basic assumptions and established beliefs. This core reaches outward through the values and behavioural norms that are recognized, responded to, and maintained by members of the culture. The values and norms, in turn, influence the choices and other actions taken by cultural members. Finally, culturally guided action produces artefacts. Schein claims that when new members are brought into a culture, they are either selected on the basis of the match between their values and those of the culture, or they are socialized to accept cultural values.

The relevance of this theory to the study cannot be overstated because every actions and inactions of the cultured members of the organization is based on the generally agreed organizational policies commonly invented, discovered, and developed by all the stakeholder as a guiding principles and the behavioural styles of members to show that there is agreement within an organization with respect to the norms to promote achievement in the organization and humanistic and self- actualizing thinking. This generally agreed guiding principle called organizational policies is what Schein describe as basic assumption, invented, discovered and developed to cope with its problems of external adaptation and internal integration

Cultures change, but only when new values are brought in from outside the culture, for instance by the decree or example of top management. However, Schein emphasizes that new values will be incorporated into basic assumptions only after they have proved their worth in terms of desired organizational outcomes. Only when members of the culture can see their benefit, will new values become taken for granted and drop to the level of unconscious assumptions. From the point of view offered by Schein's model, culture appears to be driven from the inside out from the depths of unconscious assumptions, values, and norms to the surface where numerous artefacts can be observed. But this is not the end of the story; the arrows in Schein's model point both ways. At the same time that values and assumptions’ are pushing their way "up" to the level of artefacts, the artefacts are being interpreted in ways that can transform the very values and assumptions that produced them in the first place. This happens because artefacts and norms are consciously and creatively used by the members of a culture to express their identity and to formulate and pursue their purposes.

According to Schein's (2010), every members of a culture believes on its values and kowtow to cultural- norms because their principal beliefs and assumptions’ cultivate and shore up these 'norms and values.’ The ‘norms and values,’ in turn, encourage activities that produce surface-level artefacts. Artefacts are further extensions or expressions of the same cultural core that maintains the values and norms. While values specify what is important to the members of a culture, norms establish what sorts of behaviour they can expect from one another. In short, values define what is valued, while norms make clear what it takes to be considered normal or abnormal. The link between values and norms is that the behaviours that norms sanction (that is, reward or punish) usually can be traced to outcomes that are valued. For example, the norms

about talking loudly in public, cutting in line, etc. might be traced to a cultural value for courtesy to others. Norms about wearing formal business attire (e.g., suits and ties) and not displaying any emotion while at work may indicate a value for self-discipline or for conformity.

Organizational Culture

Culture simply refers to people ways of life at a given point in time. It comprises of belief, norms, values and behavioural pattern that is acquire in the society and learnt from the other members of the society. Organizational culture is the sum of beliefs, customs, and traditions values shared by the members of the organization. The culture of the organization is not seen, it represents the totality of the way of life of a people that is not visible to the eye but serves as a very influential instrument that shapes or determine what happens within an organization. Organizational culture therefore, is seen as the personality of a group that guides the attitude and way of life of organizational member. Kumar (2006) stated that when people join an organization, they bring with them peculiar values and behaviour which they learnt. Just as society shapes human behavior, an organization also shapes employees behaviours that suites the prevalent set of norms and behaviour in the organization through the acceptance of organization indispensable attitudes and beliefs of people and their work conditions which becomes its organizational culture. According to Igwe (2000), every organization has its own culture which is used to transmit important norms, value, assumptions and activities that govern the productive behaviour of its members toward the achievement of organizational goal”, every man spends the major part of his life in the organization within which he works.

Cummings (2008) literature has revealed that organization culture is the sum of the assumptions that a given group has invented, discovered in learning-to-cope with the environment in which they find themselves and as a means to cope with their problems. O'Reilly and Chatman (1996) stated that culture functions as a boundary-defining role; this means, it create-distinctions between one organization and others. It conveys a sense of identity for organization members.

Culture facilitates the generation of commitment to something bigger than one's self interest. Fourth, it accelerates social system stability. Culture is the glue that helps grip the organization together by providing appropriate standards for what employees should say and do. Finally culture serves as a sense making and control mechanism that guides and shapes the attitude and behaviour of employees.

A school is a system and a complex organization. It is not just an arrangement of blocks Zinc called building with people inside, but a system with different parts and each part is dependent upon the other part reacting and relating to each other for change to exist. Sarason (1990) noted that a school is part of a larger “system”, and there are boundaries- of varying-potency and permeability. School culture is an all-encompassing element of schools, it permeates everything within the schools which comprises of the way people act, how they dress, what they talk, their coordination with each other, and how the staff feel about their work and their students, and how students feel about the school.

School culture means set of norms,' values' and beliefs,' rituals' and ceremonies,' symbols' and stories' that make up the “persona” of the school. These un-written prospect build up over- time as lecturers, administrators, parents, and students work together, solve problems, deal with challenges and, at times cope with failures. For instance, every school has a set of expectations about what can be discussed at staff meeting, what constitutes good teaching

techniques, or lecturing techniques, how ready the staff is to change, and the importance of staff development (Peterson, 2002).

A school's culture be it vibrant, adaptive, and thriving, or toxic and dying affects everything associated with the school (Jackson, 1993), school's culture include the obvious element of schedules, curricular, demographics, and policies, as well as the social interactions that occur within those structures which gives the school its look and feel as friendly, elite, competitive, inclusive. Reforms that go all-out for educational brilliance may fail except they are meaningfully linked to the school's peculiar culture which is a key piece in accountability and school success. Culture affect what people focus on, what they think is important, and where they are paying the most attention.

School culture is not limited to what happened within the school only but the mutual experiences both within and outside the school, such as traditions and celebrations, a sense of community, of family and team, it can be viewed as the implicit set of beliefs that determines the nature of how group perform the job within organization (Deal & Kennedy, 1983) and the means of which a school establishes self-identity. This may be due to the relationship that exists between leadership and culture, which Schein (1992) described as 'conceptually entertained; it follows then that since each school has its leader, it also has its own culture. Culture describes the holistic activities and 'ways of being and doing' of those who work in or participate on a regular basis within the school. School culture is not a system of formal written rules, but it is composed of invisible rules and customs which consciously and/or unconsciously maneuver, limit and regulate the working conditions of the school personnel and students in a narrow as well as a broad sense. Culture has it's 'tradition and a history' as well as local historical sense. The culture is influenced by the people within the organization, by the physical making environment, by the working organization, etc. School culture is an intangible, subtle element with vary composite concept.

An organization's culture could be strong or weak, it is regarded as strong when the set of norms and values are widely shared and strongly hold throughout the organization while it is weak when the reverse is the case (O'Reilly, 1989; Gerdon & Ditmosa, 1992; O'Reilly & Chafman, 1996). The more members that accept the core values the greater and stronger the culture, this implied that, strong culture enhances behavioural reliability, therefore, it could be a prevailing means of unspoken control which can be a substitute for formality (Robbins, 1990; McOliver & Nwagwu, 2000; Sorensen, 2002). Therefore, the stronger the organization's culture the lesser the need to developing formal rules to guide the conduct of employees. A strong culture enables' an organization to achieve brilliant feat. Brown (1998) and Deal and Kennedy (1983), believed on the amazing impact of a 'strong -culture' on productivity meaning that a strong culture facilitates goals alignment, leads to high level of employee motivation; is better able to learn from its past and enhance co-ordination and control within the organization.

Arguably, an organization that develops and maintains a strong organizational culture can certainly realize many benefits such as:

- Enhanced mutual trust and cooperation
- Fewer disagreement and more efficient making processes
- An informal control mechanism
- A shared understanding
- A strong sense of identification
- Facilitation of open communication

- Assisting employee in making sense of their behaviours by providing justification for behaviours.

Sergiovanni and Starrat (2002) stated that organizational culture consist of rules, norms, values, beliefs and discipline, which determine the behaviour of those in the school. It provides an organization's members with an outline for understanding and making sense of their work environment and experiences.

Culture as a concept is variously defined and conceptualized by different people. Laymen have used it as a word to indicate sophistication, as when we say that someone is very "cultured". Anthropologists have used it to refer to the customs and rituals that societies develop over the course of their history. Years ago after the research carried out by organizational managers and researchers, they are of the view that, culture is a norms and practices that organizations develop as a way of treating people base on the espoused values and principles of an organization. Managers aims at developing the "accurate kind of culture," a "culture of quality", or a "customer's service, culture" meaning that culture is a 'definite values' managers are trying to instill in their organizations. In the managerial writing, managers emphases that, culture is of paramount important for effective and efficient performance. They also believe that strong culture is the catalyst for effective organization.

Organizational culture is the set of the values, belief and behavior patterns that represent the core identity of an organization and has a significant role in making up behavior of employees (Rashid et al., 2003). In other word it includes values, concepts and patterns which are commonly learned and accepted and institutionalized by members of a group working in an organization (Lawson & Shen, 1998). Such a culture gives the members of an organization a peculiar identity and contributes to increase group commitment and consolidates their social system. Schein (1985) further indicated culture as the personality of an organization. While people cannot actually see a corporation's culture, they can infer a lot about it by observing the following:

- The fundamental philosophy of the organization
- The values that lie beneath organizational norms.
- The norms that direct behaviours
- The status accorded to certain individuals.
- The formal and informal rule that have developed for getting a task done.
- A type of language used in the organization.

The identity of an organization is of paramount important to its maintenance and growth. It acts as the basis of direction on its daily activities, the perceptions of the past and future, the correlations between the people inside and the relationships with outsiders and the decisions that are made over time (Ololube, 2024). School culture reflects a mental picture shared by all the staff. If the mental picture of the organization is not considered human sentiments, feelings, attitudes and values and preponderance of the organizational members do not make any contribution in it, it has no usefulness at all. It is the shared vision that makes whole organization united and stops people from working at cross-purposes. It is a learned body of knowledge that determines the question of the members behavior and shared meanings and symbols, which ease everyone's elucidation and indulgent of how to take steps within an

organization. Culture is the peculiar whole, the nucleus of an organization that determined how a group of people will behave. Culture is a collective belief that shape the behavior of the individual.

Mullins (2001) stated that the culture of an organization is one of the factors that tactically come together to build up an organization. He hassled that the culture of an organization, like, the culture of the people can be an inspiring factor in maximizing the value of human capital which can in the end be managed for organizational success.

An organization's culture performs four (4) functions as articulated by Smircich (1983). They are:

- Grant identity to every member of an organization: This function of the culture play the role of given a familiar identity to all of the employees of a particular organizations
- Facilitate collective commitment: culture enhances the organization to elevate the level of dedication among the employees. Employees tend to keep on with the organization for protracted periods of time, because they understand and valued the values of the organization and the environment and facilitation.
- Promote social system stability: Social system stability mirror the level at which work environment is superficial as optimistic and reinforcing, and divergence and change are managed effectively.
- Shape behavior by enhancing members: This enable the employees appreciate why the organization make a particular decision as it concern the planning of how to achieve the strategic goals of the organization and the staff.

According to Robbins and Judge (2012), organizational culture is a moderately identical perception held by the organization, this implies that every members of the culture has familiar distinctiveness, it is evocative, it can differentiate one organization from another and it unites individual, group and organization system variables.

Effective Administration of Universities

Effective according to Long man Dictionary of contemporary English New Edition for Advanced Learners is the successful, and working in the way that was intended. It also simply means the action that achieves its objective base on the identified and strategies planned to meet them. School as an organization can achieve its objectives through the process of planning. Effectiveness in general sense, means the accomplishment of set objective; or the extent to which the internal functioning of the school or an organization is able to achieve its goals and objectives in providing quality and satisfactory service to its patrons within its limited resources. Organizational effectiveness therefore reflects the internal functioning of an enterprise. The commitment to goals, objectives and ethical standards, the efficiencies of practices, processes and the perfect flow of work and information.

The concept of effectiveness has linked to several disciplines which the field of education is one of those disciplines. In education, effectiveness is a very broad concept which covers purpose effort and accomplishment. University education which is the focus of this research is a critical level of education that is saddled with the responsibility of providing the much needed

skilled manpower for any society. University administrators are the engine room of the universities because they form the vital workforce within the universities and are made up of human resources who utilize material and financial resources to accomplish set academic goals through effectiveness. According to the Federal Ministry of Education and Youth Development (1993:p283) “effectiveness is the extent to which the set goals or objectives of the school programme are accomplished and can be seen in relation to either quality or quantity and equality of educational instruction given in a school”.

An effective school is one that promotes the progress of its students in a broad range of intellectual, social and emotional outcomes, where students progress advance than might be expected from knowledge of their backgrounds. To be effective, schools require learning and teaching of the highest quality. A school can be classified as effective if there is congruence between its objectives and achievements and thus adds extra value to its student’s outcomes, staff and the society in companion with the other schools pursuing similar goals.

Effective administration of universities simply refers to the degree to which universities are able to achieve and accomplish their pre-determined objectives. It is not just about students passing semesters and academic section examinations. It concerned every progress of students in terms of attainment in other domains of learning (the affective and the psychomotor domains). According to Bandele (2002), these other domains, apart from contributing to the cognitive achievement, also made the recipient of the education system live a satisfied life and contribute meaningfully to the development of the society.

According to Ololube et al. (2018), effective administration of universities depends on the universities leader with values and good character who are saddled with enormous responsibilities and the value, they establish and promote that will input the institutional culture and success. According to him, institutional values such as integrity, effectiveness, competence, honesty, accountability and fairness usually determine how an institution functions. University leaders’ roles are sacred and indispensable in the development of institutional culture, as such; they are predictable to set up positive values that will oversee how other members function. They guarantee honesty, fairness and respect for subordinate members. They are conscious of quality, competence and committed to provide excellent services through the embracement of strong values, moral standards, discipline and ethical codes.

Organizational Shared Belief and Effective administration of Public Universities

Beliefs can be seen as a product of experiences, reflections or generalizations which can be influence by both internal and external agents. All organizations have their peculiar set of basic beliefs and values (also called moral codes), shared by most of its members. These are the imagery of organizational reality, and form the basis of defining the right or wrong in the organization. In an organization, for instance, if the predominant belief is that meeting the customers' demands is essential for success, any behavior which supposedly meets these criteria is acceptable, even if it violates the established rules and procedures. Beliefs spotlight organizational energies toward certain actions, while discouraging the other behavioral patterns. These are the foundation of all organizational cultures. They are a set of beliefs about what makes the organization successful and unsuccessful. They are developed over time and through experience. Eventually they combine to form the organization's "success formula. Deal and Kennedy (1982) asserted that beliefs are more visible than values. They affect daily business and tend to characterize the performance of the organization. Beliefs appeared explicitly, or, in

the surface behaviour of the educators. Beliefs are what a culture defends and view as the guiding forces in their action; Beliefs are what one accepts emotionally as inherently true.

Lasear (1995) in his study observed that shared belief affect delegation, monitoring and communication within the organization. Shared beliefs are often considered as an important aspect of an organizational culture, it exist in an organization as a way of life for organizational members; stable over time; strong impact on performance and satisfaction. Organizational shared belief is a slow process. An organization that can identify its core belief has created a framework for monitoring whether strategies and activities are aligned with its core value.

Behavioural Norms and Effective administration of Public Universities

A norm is a generalized disposition to the world shared by members of a community. When its condition is met, a norm generates a prepositional attitude which may, but not necessarily will, affect the subject's behaviours. Norms reflect regularities in the behaviours of members in an organization, allowing them to coordinate their actions. Behavioural Norm is one of the most important elements of organizational culture. They describe the nature of expectations which impinge on the members' behaviour. Behavioural norms determine how the members will behave, interact and relate with each other. The group norms determine whether or not one can openly disagree with superior, or whether or not people can be friendly with employees in other departments. Behaviours of employees are an important parameter while promoting the organizational culture. The enforcement of behavioral norms also weeds out those members who do not "fit" in the organization. Norms are based on values and are guides to conduct, usually framed as rules, prescriptions, or standards to be followed by people who occupy specified roles. In each school certain behavioural patterns become established. These are not the result of any formal agreement or arrangement between teachers, but develop from socially accepted or reinforced behaviour of the teachers (Deal Peterson, 1999). Norms exist in every organization and governs how members behave, think, make judgments and perceive the world. The shared norms are what defined a culture or subculture. A subculture may be a team who know how to work effectively together, and their norms include a solution to their organizational problems.

Norms can be represented in all kinds of signs, whether in documents, oral communication or behaviours, in order to preserve, to spread and to follow them. However, one cannot always put hands conveniently on a norm, as one might grasp a document that carries information through an organization. A norm is more like a field of force that makes the members of the community tend to behave or think in a certain way. Norms represents the ways of doing things in an organization; the rules, tasks and standards of the organization. Examples: Dress codes or ways of addressing superiors/subordinates, leading ethics, etc. These are patterns of behaviours or actions, routines, or traditions that are performed on a regular basis by most participants in a cultural scene, such as a school. Behavioural norms are the mode, or most frequent way of doing things. Those who follow these norms are perceived to "fit in" and those who resist them tend to stand out from the crowd. Stewart (2007) opined that an organization's cultural norms strongly affect all who are involved in the organization. Those norms are almost invisible, but if we would like to improve performance and profitability, norms are one of the first places to look.

Although not considered to be formal laws within society, norms still work to promote a great deal of social control. Social norms can be enforced formally (e.g., through sanctions) or informally (e.g., through body language and non-verbal communication cues.) Because

individuals often derive physical or psychological resources from group membership, groups are said to control discretionary stimuli; groups can withhold or give out more resources in response to members' adherence to group norms, effectively controlling member behaviour through rewards and operant conditioning (Hackmari, 1992). Social psychology research has found out that the more an individual values group-controlled resources or the more an individual sees group membership as central to his definition of self, the more likely he is to kowtow (Hackmari, 1992). Social norms also allow you to assess what behaviours the group deems important to its existence or survivals since they represent a codification of belief; groups generally do not punish members or create norms over actions which they care little about (Hackmari, 1992). According to Feldman (2011), norms in every culture create conformity that allows for people to become socialized to the culture in which they live. As social beings, individuals learn when and where it is appropriate to say certain things, to use certain words, to discuss certain topics or wear certain clothes, and when it is not. Thus, knowledge about cultural norms is important for impressions (Kamau, 2009).

METHODS

The design of this study was correlational study. The purpose of this design was to carry out an investigation on the relationship that exists between organizational culture and effective administration of public universities in Rivers State.

The population comprised all the vice-chancellors as well as academic and non-teaching staff in the three (3) public universities in Rivers State such as Ignatius Ajuru University of Education with 986 academic and non-teaching staff, Rivers State University with 1691 academic and non-teaching staff and University of Port Harcourt with 2891 academic and non-teaching staff respectively. The total population therefore embraced 3 vice-chancellors and 5565 academic and non-teaching from three public universities in Rivers State as mentioned above.

The sample of the study consisted of three hundred and seventy three staff (373) in the three public universities in Rivers State (3 Vice chancellors, 200 Academic and 170 Non-teaching staff) who were stratified by the location of schools in the three public universities in Rivers State. This sample size was selected using Taro Yamane method of sample size selection which represent 6.7 percent of the total population.

The instrument for the study is a questionnaire structured in two parts. Part one addresses organizational culture tagged organizational culture questionnaire (OCQ) while part two addresses effective administration tagged effective administration of public universities questionnaire (EAPUQ). The questionnaire will be based on four point likert rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA)-4, Agree (A)-3, Disagree (D)-2, and Strongly Disagree (SD)-1. All items with the criterion mean of 2.50 and above will be accepted while items with a criterion mean less than 2.50 will be rejected.

To ensure the validity of the instrument, a draft questionnaire was submitted to the lecturers in the Department of Educational Management of the Ignatius Ajuru University of Education for moderation and validation after which their comments, suggestions and recommendations were used to draft the final instrument. This is to ensure that the instruments really measure what it supposed to measure.

The reliability of the instrument was based on test-retest method where copies of the questionnaire were administered to two groups of professionals in public tertiary institution that are not part of the actual study. Each set was re-administered to the same group of lecturers after

two weeks. Cronbach alpha was used on data collated to determine the internal consistency of the instrument in order to get the reliability coefficient of .750.

The researcher administered the questionnaires to the head of department and other staff of the sampled universities on pre-determined dates with the help of two other assistant to ensure high level of distribution and collection of the instrument.

Descriptive statistics (Mean and standard deviation) was used to analyze the research questions; Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to analyze the hypotheses at .05 level of significance, while Cronbach Alpha coefficient was used to determine the reliability index. All statistical analysis was done using the statistical package of the social sciences (SPSS) version 21 of a computer programme.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: What is the relationship between the organizational shared beliefs and the effective administration of public universities in Rivers State?

Table 1: Respondents answer to the relationship between the organizational shared beliefs and the effective administration of public universities in Rivers State

S/N	Items	N	Mean	SD	Remarks
1	Regards people orientation	373	3.5282	.49988	Agree
2	Believes in outcome orientation	373	3.5684	.49597	Agree
3	Learning occur best in a conducive environment where stakeholder are mutually supportive.	373	3.7373	.44071	Agree
4	School program have real-life application	373	3.6327	.48271	Agree
5	We believe in good relationship and team spirit.	373	3.5684	.49597	Agree
Grand Mean			3.6070	.48304	Agree

Table 1 shows the data representation and analysis for the relationship between the organizational shared beliefs and the effective administration of public universities in Rivers State. Respondents agreed in all the items in research question one that organizational shared beliefs are related to the effective administration of public universities in Rivers State through Regards for people orientation, Believing in outcome orientation, Learning occurs best in a conducive environment where stakeholder are mutually supportive, School program have real-life application, and believing in good relationship and team spirit. This is evident in the grand mean of 3.6070 greater than 2.5 criterion mean.

Research Question 2: What is the relationship between the organizational behavioural norms and effective administration of public universities in Rivers State?

Table 2: Respondents answer to the relationship between the organizational behavioural norms and effective administration of public universities in Rivers State

S/N	Items	N	Mean	SD	Remarks
6.	Punctuality is key	373	3.5818	.49393	Agree
7.	Our teaching is base on curriculum	373	3.5603	.49701	Agree
8.	The school has clear objectives that are understand by all	373	3.7239	.44769	Agree

9.	Accountability is our watch dog	373	3.7962	.40333	Agree
10.	We do the right thing at the right time	373	3.6354	.48197	Agree
Grand Mean			3.6595	.46478	Agree

Table 2 shows the data representation and analysis for the relationship between the organizational behavioural norms and the effective administration of public universities in Rivers State. Respondents agreed in all the items in research question two that organizational behavioural norms are related to the effective administration of public universities in Rivers State. Respondents strongly agreed that punctuality is the key, teaching is based on curriculum, Accountability is the watch dog and when staffs do the right thing at the right time, the school equally has clear objectives that are understand by all. This is seen in the grand mean of 3.6595 greater than 2.5 criterion mean.

Testing of Hypotheses

Ho1. There is no significant relationship between organizational shared beliefs and effective administration of public universities in Rivers State.

Table 3: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient Analysis for the relationship between organizational shared beliefs and effective administration of public universities in Rivers State

		Shared Beliefs	Effective Administration
Shared Beliefs	Pearson Correlation	1	.918**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	373	373
Effective Administration	Pearson Correlation	.918**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	373	373

Table 3 revealed the results of correlation, where correlation value $r = .918$, $p < .000$, indicating a significant relationship between shared values and effective administration of public universities in Rivers State. Thus, the hypothesis one was rejected.

Ho2. There is no significant relationship between behavioural norms and effective administration of public universities in Rivers State.

Table 4: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient Analysis Correlations for the relationship between behavioural norms and effective administration of public universities in Rivers State

		Behavioural Norms	Effective Administration
Behavioural Norms	Pearson Correlation	1	.640**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	373	373
Effective Administration	Pearson Correlation	.640**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	373	373

Table 4 revealed the results of correlation, where correlation value $r = .640$, $p < .000$, indicating a significant relationship between behavioral norms and effective administration of public universities in Rivers State. Thus, the hypothesis two was rejected.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Organizational Shared Beliefs and Effective Administration of Public Universities

Hypothesis one stated that “There is no significant relationship between organizational shared beliefs and effective administration of public universities in Rivers State”, the Pearson correlation results where correlation value $r = .918$, $p < .000$, which revealed that there is a significant relationship between organizational shared beliefs and the effective administration of public universities in Rivers State. Thus, the null hypothesis one was rejected. This finding is in agreement with Olorube (2024) who asserted that Shared beliefs are often considered as an important aspect of an organizational culture, it exists in an organization as: a way of life for organizational members; stable over time; strong impact on performance and satisfaction. Organizational shared belief is a slow process. An organization that can identify its core belief has created a framework for monitoring whether strategies and activities are aligned with its core value. This implies that for universities to effectively manage and administer their activities, they must have a common organizational belief that guides their operation and administration.

Proving more conceptual backing to this finding, Lasear (1999) in a study observed that shared belief affect delegation, monitoring and communication within the organization. For universities to be run effectively, successfully managing human and material resources that affect both staff and students’ welfare and wellbeing, communication and monitoring are effective mechanisms to achieve objectives.

Behavioural Norms and Effective Administration of Public Universities

Hypothesis two stated that “There is no significant relationship between organizational behavioural norms and effective administration of public universities in Rivers State”, the Pearson correlation results where correlation value $r = .640$, $p < .000$, revealed that there is a significant relationship between organizational behavioural norms and the effective administration of public universities in Rivers State. Thus, the null hypothesis two was rejected. This finding is in concert with Feldrnan (2011) who opined that norms in every culture create conformity that allows for people to become socialized to the culture in which they live. Norms reflect regularities in the behaviours of members in an organization, allowing them to coordinate their actions. Behavioural Norm is one of the most important elements of organizational culture. They describe the nature of expectations which impinge on the members' behavior. As social beings, individuals learn when and where it is appropriate to say certain things, to use certain words, to discuss certain topics or wear certain clothes, and when it is not. Thus, knowledge about cultural norms is important for impressions (Kamau, 2009). Since human resources of universities are comprised of complex human elements, hence, effective administration requires that behavior norms are established to give direction to both students and staff. According to Stewart (2007), an organization's cultural norms strongly affect all who are involved in the organization. Those norms are almost invisible, but if we would like to improve performance and profitability, norms are one of the first places to look.

CONCLUSION

The findings of the study revealed that organizational culture which includes prevalent organizational culture, organizational shared beliefs, and behavioural norms, are significantly related to effective administration of public universities in Rivers State, this goes to show that much is expected on the part of university administrators since, organizational culture in public universities refers to the pervasive system of values, beliefs, and norms that exists and can encourage and discourage effective performance, the onus lies on institutional leaders and managers to establish a formidable and well-coordinated organizational culture to ensure effective administration of the schools especially at the tertiary level.

Recommendations

In view of the findings and conclusions of the study, the followings recommendations were made:

- The strong behavioural norms in accordance to the universities code of conduct must be adhere to by all the universities staff. University management should initiate periodic organizational reorientation and value alignment workshops aimed at redefining and reinforcing shared beliefs that promote teamwork, accountability, and institutional excellence. Such programs should engage all categories of staff (academic and non-teaching) to ensure that institutional goals and values are clearly understood and integrated into daily administrative practices. This will help translate shared beliefs into tangible administrative outcomes.
- University authorities should develop clear behavioural policies that articulate acceptable workplace ethics, communication standards, and conduct expectations. Leadership at all levels (vice-chancellors, deans, and heads of departments) should model these norms consistently to foster a culture of professionalism and integrity. Embedding these behavioural standards into performance evaluation and reward systems will help ensure adherence and enhance administrative effectiveness.

REFERENCES

- Ahiau, A. (1999). *The African industrial man*. CIMRAT Publications
- Bande, S. O. (2002). Administration of continuous assessment in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. *Journal of Educational Foundations and Management*, 1(1), 289-296.
- Brown, A. (1998). *Organizational culture*. Financial times/Pitman Publishing.
- Cummings, T. G. (2008). *Handbook of organization development*. Sage
- Deal, T. E., & Peterson, K. D. (1999). *Shaping school culture: The heart of leadership*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- Deal, T. E., & Kennedy, A. A. (1983). Culture: A new look through old lenses. *The Journal of Applied Behavioural Science*, 19(4), 498-505.
- Federal Ministry of Education and Youth Development (1993). *Better schools management: lead teacher education and resource material*, Lagos: Federal Ministry of Education and Youth Development.

- Feldman, M.S. (2011). Theorizing practice and practicing theory. *Organization science*, 23(5), 1240-1253.
- Gordon, G. G. & N. DiTmosa, (1992). Predicting corporate performance from organizational culture. *Journal of Management Studies*, 29: 783-798.
- Hackmari, J. R. (1992). Group influences on individuals in organizations. In M. D. Dunnette & L.M. Hough (Eds.), *Handbook of industrial and organizational psychology* (Vol. 3). Palo Alto: Consulting Psychologists Press, 234-245.
- Hargreaves, D. H. (1995). *School culture, Effective administration of secondary schools and school improvement. Effective administration of secondary schools and School Improvement*, 6(1), 23-46.
- Igwe, N. (2000). Effectiveness of corporate social responsibility (CSR) reporting in enhancing corporate image: *European Journal of Business and Social Science* 4(5), 01-11, 2015.
- Jackson, F. R. (1993). Seven strategies to support a culturally responsive pedagogy, *Journal of Reading* 37(4), 298-303.
- Kamau, C. (2009). Strategizing impression management in corporations: cultural knowledge as capital. In D. Harorimana (Ed.), *Cultural implications of knowledge sharing, management and transfer: identifying competitive advantage* (pp. 60-80). Information Science Reference.
- Kumar, D.M. (2006) *Impact of organizational culture upon employees and employer's behaviour*. Unpublished thesis Mahatma Gandhi University.
- Lasear, E. P. (1999). Culture and language. *Journal of Political Economy*, 107 (S6), S95-S126.
- Lawson, R. B. & Shen, Z. (1998). *Organizational psychology: Foundation and applications*. Oxford University press.
- McOliver, F. O. & Nwagwu, N. A. (2000). *Organizational theory and development: Issues and perspectives* (1st Ed.). Festa Printing.
- Mullins, L. J. (2001). *Hospitality and management and organizational behavior* (14th Ed.) Essex: Pearson Education Limited.
- O'Reilly, C. (1989). *Corporations, culture and commitment: Motivation and social control in organizations*, 31(4), 9-25.
- O'Reilly, C. H., & Chatman, J. A. (1996). *Culture as social control: corporations, cults, and commitment*. Elsevier Science/JAI press.
- Ololube, N. P. (2006). *Teacher education, school effectiveness and improvement: a study of academic and professional qualification on teachers' job effectiveness in Nigerian secondary schools*. Doctoral Dissertation, December 2006. University of Helsinki, Faculty of Behavioral Sciences, Department of Applied Sciences of Education, Helsinki: University of Helsinki Press.
- Ololube, N. P. (2024). *Institutional leadership: Laying the foundation for success*. Pearl Publications.
- Ololube, N. P., Elechi, S. K., & Uriel, O. A. (2018). Education a Leadership and management (ELM): Institutional leaders Value Functions for Effective Management of Universities. In N.P Ololube (ED.), *Encyclopedia of institutional leadership, policy and management* (pp.111-133) Pearl Publishers.
- Peterson, K. D. (2002). Positive or negative. *Journal of Staff Development*, 23(3), 10-15
- Rashid, M. Z. A., Sambasivan, M., Johari, J. (2003). The influence of corporate culture and organizational commitment on performance. *Journal of Management Development*, 22(8), 708-28.

- Robbins, S. P. (1990). *Organizational theory: Structures, Designs, And Applications* (3rd Ed.), Prentice Hall.
- Robbins, S. P., & Judge, T. (2012). *Essentials of organizational behavior* (14th Ed.).Upper Prentice Hall.
- Robert, O. (2014). *Education management in Nigeria: A Functional approach*. Harey Publication.
- Schein, E. H. (2011). *Leadership and organizational culture*. Wiley.
- Schein, E. H., (2004). *Organizational culture and leadership* (3rd Ed.) John Wiley and Sons.
- Schein, E. H. (1992). *How can organizations learn faster? The problem of entering the green room*. Jossey-Bass.
- Schein, E. H. (2010). *Organizational culture and leadership* (Vol. 2). John Wiley and sons.
- Schein, E. H., (1985). *Organizational culture and leadership*. Jossey-Boss.
- Schwartz, S. H. (1994). *Beyond individualism/collectivism: New cultural dimensions of values*. Sage Publication.
- Sergiovanni, T. J. & Starrat, R. J. (2002). *Supervision : A redefinition* (7th Ed.). McGraw-Hill.
- Smireich, L. (1983). Concepts of culture and organizational analysis. *Administrative Science Quarter/volume*, 28, 339-359.
- Sorensen J. B (2002). The strength of corporate culture and the reliability of firm performance. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 47, 70-91.
- Stewart, J. (2007). Leader-member exchange (LMX) theory of leadership and HRD: Development of units of theory and laws of interaction. *Leadership and Organization Development Journal*, 28(6), 531-551.